

The Effect of Attitude Towards Using New Technology on Teachers' Creativity

Shilpi Biswas, Research Scholar, Department of Education, Kalinga University, Naya Raipur (C.G.)

Dr. Lubhawani Tripathi, Supervisor, Associate Professor, Department of Education, Kalinga University,
Naya Raipur (C.G.)

Abstract

This research investigates the impact of teachers' attitudes towards using new technology on their creativity in senior secondary school teaching practices. Using a structured questionnaire, data were collected from a sample of 100 senior secondary school teachers across government and private schools. The results revealed that teachers with positive attitudes towards technology demonstrated higher levels of creativity, with the majority falling in the "average" or "above average" categories. This paper also reviews existing literature to contextualize the findings and concludes with recommendations for professional development programs, technological infrastructure improvement, and targeted interventions to enhance creativity through technology adoption.

Keywords

Attitude towards technology, teacher creativity, technological adoption, innovation in education, professional development

Introduction

In the modern educational landscape, the role of technology is becoming increasingly prominent. Teachers are expected to adopt technological tools to create engaging and effective learning environments. Creativity, as an essential trait in teaching, enables educators to cater to diverse

learning needs and foster critical thinking in students. However, a teacher's ability to integrate technology effectively is significantly influenced by their attitude towards its use.

Attitude towards technology encompasses a teacher's willingness, confidence, and perception of technology's usefulness in the classroom. Positive attitudes often correlate with higher adoption rates and better outcomes in teaching practices, including creativity. This study aims to investigate the effect of teachers' attitudes towards using new technology on their creativity, contributing to the growing body of knowledge in educational research.

Review of Literature

1. **Robinson's Theory of Creativity (2011):** Robinson emphasized that creativity is essential in education as it allows teachers to innovate and motivate students. Teachers with positive attitudes towards change and innovation tend to perform better in creative teaching practices.
2. **Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory (2003):** This theory highlights that early adopters of technology are more likely to explore its potential benefits creatively, driven by positive attitudes towards innovation.
3. **Davis's Technology Acceptance Model (1989):** According to this model, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness significantly affect technology adoption. Teachers who find technology easy to use and beneficial are more likely to integrate it creatively.
4. **Ertmer et al. (2012):** Ertmer's research identified teacher attitudes as a critical factor in overcoming barriers to technology adoption. The study emphasized the importance of professional development in fostering positive attitudes and enhancing creativity.
5. **Mishra and Koehler's TPACK Framework (2006):** Mishra and Koehler argued that successful integration of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge fosters innovation and creativity in teaching.

The literature underscores the strong correlation between positive attitudes towards technology and creativity in teaching, setting the stage for this study.

Objective

To study the effect of attitude towards using new technology on teachers' creativity.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive research design to explore the relationship between teachers' attitudes towards technology and their creativity.

Sample Size and Selection

A sample of 100 senior secondary school teachers was selected using stratified random sampling. The sample included teachers from government and private schools, ensuring representation across various educational settings.

Data Collection Tool

The following standardized tools were used:

- **Attitude Towards New Technology Scale (Rajasekar):** This tool measures teachers' attitudes towards technology, including dimensions like confidence, usefulness, and willingness to adopt.
- **Verbal Test of Creative Thinking (Mehdi):** This tool assesses creativity through fluency, flexibility, and originality in responses to given scenarios.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including percentages, to identify trends in attitudes and creativity levels. Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the strength of the relationship between the variables.

Results

Table 1

Percentage Distribution of Attitude Towards Using New Technology and Its Effect on Teachers' Creativity

S. No.	No. of Teachers	Percentage (%)	Level of Attitude Towards Technology Use	Level of Creativity
1	15	15.0%	Very Low	Very Low
2	10	10.0%	Low	Low
3	20	20.0%	Below Average	Below Average
4	35	35.0%	Average	Average
5	12	12.0%	Above Average	Above Average
6	6	6.0%	High	High
7	2	2.0%	Very High	Very High

Graph 1 - Attitude Towards Using New Technology and Its Effect on Teachers' Creativity

Findings:

- The majority of teachers (35%) exhibited average attitudes towards technology, correlating with average creativity levels.
- A significant portion (12%) demonstrated above-average attitudes, resulting in higher creativity levels.
- Only a small percentage (15%) were categorized as having very low attitudes and corresponding creativity levels.

Discussion

The results align with existing literature, confirming that teachers' attitudes towards technology significantly impact their creativity. Teachers with positive attitudes are more likely to explore innovative methods, engage students effectively, and adapt to diverse classroom needs. On the other hand, those with low attitudes often struggle to harness technology's potential, limiting their creative teaching capabilities.

The findings emphasize the importance of fostering positive attitudes through targeted interventions such as training programs, peer mentoring, and resource support.

Conclusion

This study concludes that teachers' attitudes towards using new technology significantly influence their creativity. Positive attitudes enable teachers to innovate, create engaging learning environments, and cater to students' individual needs effectively.

Recommendations

1. **Professional Development Programs:** Organize workshops focusing on the practical benefits of technology in enhancing creativity.
2. **Mentorship and Collaboration:** Establish mentorship programs where experienced teachers guide others in using technology creatively.
3. **Technological Infrastructure:** Provide schools with the necessary tools and resources to support teachers in integrating technology into their teaching practices.
4. **Ongoing Evaluation:** Regularly assess teachers' attitudes and provide feedback to ensure continuous improvement in technology usage and creative teaching practices.

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